
Deep Learning Approaches for Identifying Anti-Refugee Speech in Spanish Texts

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Abstract

This study addresses the automatic detection of negative anti-refugee messages in Spanish texts, using language models based on pre-trained Transformers models. Despite numerous studies on hate speech detection, few have concentrated on Spanish, particularly regarding hostility towards refugees. To fill this void, we developed *hateRADAR-es*, a new corpus of Spanish-language tweets manually annotated by sociologist and social workers experts to identify the presence or absence of hateful content directed at refugees. This dataset has been made available to the research community to encourage further investigation. A comprehensive experimental framework to tackle this challenge, composed of several stages to achieve language models with a high efficacy in detecting such messages, is presented. Several traditional machine learning algorithms and pre-trained transformer-based language models are evaluated, demonstrating that the current language models outperform traditional models. To address the class imbalance issue in the data, data augmentation techniques are applied, and extensive experimentation is carried out to find the best values for the hyperparameters of the language models to achieve better performance. In the evaluation process, an ensemble of the fine-tuned models BETO, XLM-RoBERTa, and RoBERTa-large achieved the best results, with an accuracy of 0.891, an F-measure of 0.860, and an AUC-ROC of 0.892. These findings underscore the effectiveness of combining multiple models into an ensemble to handle the complexity and nuances of hate speech on social media, offering a promising direction for future adaptations and applications of language models in specific hate contexts.

Keywords

Deep Learning, Language Models, Transformers, Social Media, Twitter, Hate Speech, Refugees

I. Introduction

In recent decades, the diversity of international conflicts, as well as natural disasters, have led to a worldwide increase in the number of refugees, which has been on the rise since 2011 and reached a significant peak in 2015 in the context of the so-called “refugee crisis” (Ghosh, 2022; Hinz et al., 2023; González-Baquero et al., 2023; UNHCR, 2022). The massive arrival of refugees to a territory is commonly accompanied by different changes and the emergence of fears and apprehensions on the part of the population (Ghosh, 2022). On the other hand, the increased use of the Internet and the loudspeaker of social media produces the growth of online hate speech over the last years (European-Commission, 2021; González-Baquero et al., 2023; Arcila-Calderón et al., 2022; Gualda and Rebollo, 2016; Rebollo, 2021). Aspects such as anonymity, disinhibition, or the feeling of impunity on the Internet contribute to the spread of hatred. Likewise, political interest and violent extremism propagate and incite hatred directed at individuals and their communities, mobilizing emotions and contributing to the polarization of different sectors of society.

Although there is no universally accepted definition of the term hate speech (Weber, 2009; United-Nations, 2021), it can be understood as those forms of expression that are disseminated and that incite, promote, or justify hatred or intolerance (European-Commission, 2016, 2021, 2023) directed against a person or a particular group of persons based on their identity (real or perceived), be it related to their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, color, descent, gender or other identity factor (United-Nations, 2021; European-Commission, 2021), as would be the case of hate speech directed at refugees.

It is essential to mention that among the main types of hate speech is Islamophobic speech, as the European Commission, the United Nations, and other organizations continuously warn of the hostility received from the Muslim population (European-Commission, 2024). As (Ghosh, 2022) indicates, a growing xenoracism of an Islamophobic nature and a manifest hostility towards the Muslim community is detected in Europe, together with an atmosphere of intolerance and exclusion, which is accompanied by different hate crimes in the form of physical and verbal attacks. It is a negative discourse strongly disseminated on social platforms around specific cases (González-Baquero et al., 2023). Hate speech propagated against refugees is recurrent internationally in different Internet and social media spaces (YouTube, Facebook, Twitter or X, Instagram, and others). The harmful content is diverse. Stereotypes, prejudices, false or distorted

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information, portraying them as “villains,” “criminals,” “dangerous,” “uninvited visitors,” or other negative appellatives are propagated, sometimes subtly (Velikonja, 2022; Arcila-Calderón et al., 2022; Lotero-Echeverri and Romero-Rodriguez, 2023; Nguyen et al., 2023; Chimkhilai and Panyametheekul, 2024). These contribute to the construction and deepening of public stigmatization and otherization of individuals or groups of refugees and generate problems for societies such as racism, intolerance, and discrimination (Sánchez-Holgado et al., 2022; González-Baquero et al., 2023), increased vulnerability or risks of exploitation and marginalization of refugees (Camargo et al., 2022). Moreover, hate speech or incitement to hatred is close to hate crimes and violence. (European-Commission, 2023) has warned of the dangerous link between hate speech and violence, stating that hate speech is an extreme form of intolerance that contributes to hate crimes.

The context briefly described above justifies the need for tools for the automatic detection of hate speech directed towards refugees. This need is more pressing in the case of languages other than English, where the development of systems to monitor online content and remove abusive, offensive or hateful content has been lower, this detection being vital to fostering less bellicose environments (García-Baena et al., 2023).

The interest of automatically identifying hate speech in online texts has emerged as a critical area of research in Natural Language Processing (NLP) and computational linguistics. Various studies have focused on developing machine learning models and algorithms capable of identifying and classifying hate speech content in different languages (Mohdeb et al., 2022; Jahan and Oussalah, 2023; Gudumotu et al., 2023; Mansur et al., 2023). However, the majority of these studies have been conducted in English, with limited attention given to other languages, such as Spanish. Furthermore, the datasets available for hate speech detection are labelled for a general domain and not for a specific domain such as the refugee population. Hence, the aim of this study is to obtain a customized and effective language models to automatically identify negative messages in Spanish that are aimed at this specific group. While our focus is on tweets in Spanish, the approach outlined in this paper and the resulting findings can be applied to other languages.

For a language model to learn to detect a certain type of content from a specific domain, it is necessary to have a training dataset. To ensure that the model is effective, it is essential to ensure that the training dataset is correctly labelled. Otherwise, the results provided may be biased or incorrect. For this reason, obtaining such resources is not easy. The construction of the corpus used in this study has been carried out by sociologist and social workers experts following a meticulous manual labelling methodology, ensuring the validity of the data. This work addresses a binary classification task, where each document (tweet) is assigned a positive (“1”) or negative (“0”) label indicating the presence or absence of hateful messages towards refugees. Details on the construction of the corpus are described in the following sections.

The following items summarize the main contributions of our work:

- (i) A study on the implication of hate speech directed towards refugees and its treatment from the point of view of NLP.
- (ii) A new dataset about refugees for Spanish hate speech detection, created using Twitter (rebranded as X) as a source of information, and labelled by sociologist and social workers experts.

- (iii) A comprehensive experimental framework to obtain effective language models based on Transformers.
- (iv) An exploration of different computational methods to achieve better model performance: data augmentation, hyperparameter search, and ensemble techniques.
- (v) An error analysis, from computational and sociological perspectives, to determine future directions of the study.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: in Section II, related works are discussed, exploring prior research conducted in the field. Section III presents a new dataset in Spanish for hate speech detection towards refugees, and the annotation process. Section IV details the different approaches used to achieve the proposed task. The experimental framework developed is described in Section V. Results and error analysis are presented in Section VI. Finally, Section VII summarizes the conclusions of this study and shows future work.

II. Related Works

The automatic detection of hate speech in online platforms has attracted significant attention across various languages and contexts. While considerable work has been done in English, less focus has been given to other languages, particularly in detecting hate speech against minority groups, such as refugees in the Spanish language. (Jahan and Oussalah, 2023) provide a comprehensive systematic review of hate speech detection using NLP, highlighting the prevalence of English language studies and underscoring the need for research in other linguistic contexts. Similarly, (Mansur et al., 2023) discuss the breadth of methods used for hate speech detection on Twitter, noting that while many techniques have been developed, applications in languages other than English remain limited, emphasizing the relevance of our focus on Spanish. Advancements in machine learning models, particularly those based on deep learning, have shown promising results in text classification tasks. (Li et al., 2022) survey these developments, from traditional machine learning methods to modern deep learning techniques. Furthermore, (Garrido-Merchan et al., 2023) compare the efficacy of BERT models against traditional machine learning models in text classification tasks, providing evidence that supports the use of transformer-based language models for enhanced accuracy and generalization in hate speech detection. In addition to model comparisons, the societal impact and technological challenges of detecting hate speech are critically reviewed by (Gudumotu et al., 2023), who explore various deep learning models for identifying hate speech and bullying. This work provides insights into the complexities of implementing these models in social media platforms, which align with the challenges we address in our own research.

The detection of hate speech online has been the subject of various investigations, particularly in contexts where minorities such as migrants and refugees are frequently victimized. While significant studies exist, few address this phenomenon in the Spanish language with a specific focus on refugees. (Arcila-Calderón et al., 2022) developed classifiers using both shallow and deep learning to detect racist and xenophobic discourses directed toward migrants and refugees in Spanish. Unlike our study, their research focused on a broader range of xenophobia without constructing a specific corpus for refugees. In (Benítez-Andrades et al., 2022), the authors present a study for the automatic detection of racism and xenophobia on Twitter using deep learning

techniques. Although the results obtained, especially with transformer-based language models, are good, the authors assert that their research presents preliminary findings that need to be deeply investigated to address some weaknesses such as the size of the dataset used. Moreover, (Sánchez-Holgado et al., 2022) explored the correlation between online hate speech and the acceptance of immigrants at the provincial level in Spain. This study used social acceptance data to measure the impact of hate speech, a methodology distinct from ours, which focuses on the development and evaluation of NLP models to automatically identify hate speech on social networks.

These works complement the research presented in this study by demonstrating the diversity of approaches in the study of hate speech and highlight the importance of developing specific solutions for linguistic and cultural contexts. Our work distinguishes itself by focusing on the optimization of NLP models for the Spanish and by directly addressing the detection of hate speech toward refugees, adding a layer of specificity in the identification of such discourses on social media platforms.

III. Corpus Design and Construction

This section introduces the *hateRADAR-es* (*Anti-Hate Refugees Annotated Dataset and Analysis Resource*) dataset, a corpus of Spanish-language Twitter messages meticulously compiled for the purpose of identifying content containing both hateful and negative expressions directed towards refugees. We elaborate on the methods employed for extracting and annotating the documents, providing comprehensive statistical insights into the collection. Currently, there are few datasets in Spanish explicitly designed for identifying adverse messages directed towards refugees. Therefore, we want to offer the scientific community a useful resource for researching and deepening new approaches for the automatic detection of hate speech towards this group. Overall, we are confident that this dataset will be an invaluable resource for researchers who are seeking to understand the impact of hate speech on refugees, especially filling a gap with regard to annotated datasets on refugees in Spanish. By providing access to this data, we hope to contribute to a greater understanding of this issue and to promote positive change in our communities. The *hateRADAR-es* dataset is available on GitHub* for research purposes.

Figure 1 shows, schematically, the steps followed to build the *hateRADAR-es* dataset.

III-a. Previous Research: Data Collection and Qualitative Autocoding with ATLAS.ti

The tweets in this collection (Rebollo, 2021) were extracted using the NodeXL tool (<https://nodexl.com/>), which consists of an Excel template that allows the extraction of data from Twitter and other social networks through a search engine where the keyword or words that function as search criteria are inserted. This tool is mainly oriented to perform social network analysis (relationship between users, retweet networks, hashtags, communities, etc.) and therefore, it collects and orders the data in a structure prepared for this purpose. For example, renaming users as source and target according to their role in the social interaction. One of the fields collected by NodeXL is the “tweet” field, which contains the content of the message and is

*<https://github.com/unihuelva/NON-CONSPIRA-HATE/hateRADAR-es>

Figure 1. Process of creation of the Corpus for training: the *hateRADAR-es* dataset.

the one used to build this working collection, together with the “id”. NodeXL, at the time the tweets were exported, collected the data through the Rest API, collecting the tweets published retrospectively.

Thousands of tweets were extracted on a daily basis from the search string “refugees” in six different languages: Spanish (“refugiados”), English (“refugees”), German (“fluechtlinge”), French (“réfugiés”), Italian (“rifugiati”) and Portuguese (“refugiados”), during a period from December 2015 to December 2016 (one year). During this period, the international refugee situation worsened significantly, reaching unprecedented numbers. The main causes of this crisis were civil wars and violence in Syria, as well as in other places such as Iraq, Yemen, and sub-Saharan Africa. These conflicts forced the inhabitants of these regions to flee their homes and seek refuge in neighbouring countries or risk reaching European Union countries through irregular displacement routes. In response to this situation, the UNHCR declared it a refugee crisis (Fleming, 2015).

This serious scenario did not go unnoticed on social media, where the migration crisis became a topic of intense debate among numerous and diverse users. Twitter offered significant advantages in contributing to the debate and disseminating information owing to its immediacy and ease of following events in real-time. Users used these tools to inform themselves, socially denounce the situation, criticize government policies, and actively participate in conversations about the refugee crisis. In addition, these social media discussions contributed to increasing the visibility of the crisis, generating greater international awareness and mobilization regarding the situation of refugees.

All daily extractions were merged by language to obtain six different datasets. Once merged, any duplicated tweets were removed by taking into account the “id” of the tweet, which confers

a unique identification number to each one. In this work we have used the Spanish dataset composed of 355,810 tweets. Since our interest was not in the dissemination patterns of the tweets, we excluded retweeted messages to avoid repetition of tweets, finally obtaining a sample of 90,144 tweets.

This collection of tweet messages was previously labelled with the perspective of knowing the diversity of different discourses about refugees in different languages (Gualda and Rebollo, 2016; Rebollo, 2021). At that time, the qualitative software *Atlas.ti* (<https://atlasti.com/>) was used to study the tweets about the refugees through sociological content and thematic analysis applying automatic coding techniques in *Atlas.ti*. An extensive codebook was produced in that moment, which can be found in the annexes of (Rebollo, 2021).

III-b. Corpus Annotation: Annotation Guide, Doccano, Sampling, Tests and Annotation of Tweets

This section describes all the steps followed to reach the *hateRADAR-es* dataset.

III-b.1. Annotation Guide

While previous research (III-a) used a codebook to label the diversity of discourses on refugees, an annotation guide was explicitly developed to detect online hate speech towards refugees. This guide, designed by experts in the field, would make it easier to tackle the complex and subjective task of manually tagging our dataset. The annotation process consisted of labeling with “1” when “Hate speech towards refugees is detected in the tweet” and “0” when “Hate speech is not detected in the tweet”. At annotation, hate speech has been understood, as specified in the Section Introduction, by those forms of hate speech that incite, promote, or justify hatred or intolerance directed against a person or a particular group of persons based on their identity (real or perceived), whether related to their religion, ethnicity, nationality, race, colour, descent, gender or other identity factor, as would be the case with hate speech directed at refugees.

III-b.2. Test of Doccano as Annotation Tool

To carry out a manual labeling process by human experts, we used the *Doccano* tool (<https://github.com/doccano/doccano>), an open-source text annotation platform designed for human users. *Doccano* offers annotation functions tailored for tasks such as text classification, among others. Five annotators were trained to test this tool. Two hundred tweets were randomly extracted from the global Spanish dataset (90,000 tweets) to do this test. The complete team evaluated all the processes and results of this first test.

III-b.3. Class Imbalance and Sampling of Tweets for Annotation

After the Doccano annotation test was performed by five annotators, a class imbalance was detected in the dataset (with a deficit of “1. Hate” and a predominance of “0. Non-hate/Neutral”

tweets). As a strategy to achieve a more balanced collection to be annotated, the previous codebook on the diversity of discourses on refugees (III.a) was used to extract different tokens and regular expressions associated with hate tweets, on the one hand, and non-hate and neutral tweets on the other. Two subsamples of 250 tweets were extracted from the global dataset. One was filtered with codes relating to neutral or non-hateful messages towards refugees, and the second was filtered with negative messages towards refugees. After randomly selecting both the subsamples, 500 tweets were joined and randomly ordered before annotation. This sample of 500 tweets was used to train the two annotators and the referee before labelling 5000 tweets. The same procedure was used to select the final corpus of 5000 tweets to be annotated.

III-b.4. Corpus Annotation

In a first stage, the dataset was labeled by two experts on sociology and social work with the initial aim of distinguishing between tweets containing hate speech, racist or xenophobic discourse towards refugees (label “1”), and tweets that did not contain such an issue (label “0”). Given the subjective nature and the level of difficulty of the task, manual labeling of this dataset was facilitated with the support of the annotation guide specifically designed by domain experts (Gualda and Rebollo Díaz, 2024). The overall inter-annotation agreement during this phase reached a satisfactory correlation index of 0.66 of the Cohen’s Kappa coefficient (Artstein, 2017). Out of 5000 labeled tweets, annotators reached an 85% agreement. In a subsequent stage, tweets where there was no consensus among annotators or raised uncertainties were meticulously analyzed and evaluated by a third person, also an expert in sociology of migrations and social work, to resolve disagreements (referee). This thorough review and discussion of the most challenging classification cases assisted in addressing certain subtleties in tweets posted on Twitter in this domain. Table 1 presents various examples of annotated tweets along with a brief explanation of the label chosen by the annotators.

Figure 2. Most frequent terms (excluding search terms) used in tweets. (left) Label “1”. (right) Label “0”.

Table 1. Some examples of labelled tweets in Spanish and English, along with a brief explanation of the reason for the annotation.

Spanish tweet	English version	Label	Explanation
Esta es la mejor prueba de que JAMAS se van a occidentalizar. Islam x encima de todo! FUERA REFUGIADOS DE ESPAÑA!	This is the best proof that they will NEVER westernise. Islam above all else! REFUGEES OUT OF SPAIN!	1	This is a tweet that proposes to expel refugees, rejecting the Islam and its integration possibilities in Western societies
VERGuenza y asco de países europeos q consenten esta pederastia encubierta. STopIslam	SHAME and disgust of European countries that condone this covert paedophilia. STopIslam	1	This is a tweet associating Islam with paedophilia, rejecting European policies
El plan secreto de los refugiados musulmanes: 'islamizar Alemania' vía @user	Muslim refugees' secret plan: 'Islamise Germany' via @user	1	This tweet defends the conspiracy theory of the invasion of Europe by Islam (Eurabia) that rejects refugees
@user aparte como he dicho mientras más refugiados pues más probabilidades hay de atentados violaciones etc... caballo de Troya	@user apart, as I said, the more refugees, the more likely there are to be attacks, rapes etc... Trojan horse	1	This tweet associates refugees with attacks, rape and other negative aspects
Polonia se niega a aceptar refugiados musulmanes tras los atentados de Bruselas	Poland refuses to accept Muslim refugees after Brussels attacks.	0	This is a new about migration and border policies in Poland
#refugioderechoshumanos habéis tardado hoy en cagar, pero lo de los refugiados ya lo habéis trillado otras veces, ya no cuela piojosos	#humanrightsrefugee You've taken your time today to shit, but you've already done it before with the refugees, it doesn't work any more, you lousy licem	0	This is hate speech but it is not directed specifically at refugees
Manifestación hoy en Berlín de Neonazis y extrema derecha contra política de asilo para refugiados y contra islamización de Alemania	Neo-Nazis and right-wing extremists demonstrate today in Berlin against asylum policy for refugees and the Islamization of Germany	0	This is information about a demonstration, describing its motives
@user ¿Tú qué haces por los refugiados? PD: Lo de 'mosquita muerta' puedes llamárselo a tu madre	@user What do you do for refugees? PS: You can call your mother a 'dead mosquito'	0	It is negative speech towards another person but not specifically towards refugees

Table 2. Distribution of labels in the dataset.

Dataset	Tweets	Label 0	Label 1
hateRADAR-es	5000	3810 (76.2%)	1190 (23.8%)

III-c. Dataset Features

Once the annotation process was completed, a study was conducted on some of the most relevant features of the collection. Despite implementing a first strategy to reduce class imbalance (III.b.3), after the annotation process, there is still a significant imbalanced distribution of tweets. **Table 2** shows this distribution, indicating that 76.2% (3810) of the messages do not contain hatred towards refugees, while the remaining 23.8% (1190) contain negative content towards them.

It is important to note that, although a balance was sought in the subsets of messages without and with hateful content towards refugees, after the annotation process, a considerable imbalance has arisen regarding the labels. This is because many of the messages that were selected while searching for words with potentially negative connotations such as *violación* (rape), *invasión* (invasion), *delito* (crime) or *islamización* (Islamization), did not reveal hate messages during the annotation process and, therefore, were labelled with the label “0”.

Automated text classification becomes a challenging task when dealing with an imbalanced training dataset, necessitating the implementation of balancing techniques before applying machine learning algorithms (Padurariu and Breaban, 2019).

A study of the vocabulary used in the messages was also carried out to identify the most frequently occurring terms in this type of content. Analyses were performed on the complete dataset and separately on the subsets corresponding to each label. **Figure 2** shows the most frequent terms for each label. It can be observed that terms such as “musulmanes” (“muslims”) and “violaciones” (“rape”) frequently appear in messages containing hatred, whereas terms such as “ayuda” (“help”) and “derechos” (“rights”) are more prevalent in messages that do not contain hate.

IV. Proposed Approach

Once the data was labelled, machine learning algorithms and deep learning models were implemented to identify hate messages targeting refugees on Spanish tweets. To obtain the most effective model, a specific experimental framework described in the Subsection *V. Experimental Framework* was designed. This work includes an analysis of traditional machine learning algorithms that have demonstrated good performance in text classification in recent years (Das et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022; Tiwari and Agrawal, 2022), as well as a detailed study of several state-of-the-art language models (Chae and Davidson, 2023; Garrido-Merchan et al., 2023). Traditional machine learning algorithms investigated include Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) and Logistic Regression (LR), all of which are examined in the study by (Das et al., 2023), in addition to eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) (Babaeianjelodar et al., 2022). This broad exploration of machine and deep learning approaches allows us to identify the most promising and effective techniques for the detection of hate speech in social networks, with a particular focus on its application in the context of anti-refugee discourse on Twitter in Spanish.

In terms of deep learning algorithms (Minaee et al., 2021), Transformers (Vaswani et al., 2017) were chosen as the prominent models for this study. Transformers have emerged as the leading architectures in NLP, widely adopted in various tasks. These models undergo pre-training

using vast text corpora, enabling them to efficiently capture complex linguistic relationships. Moreover, they can be fine-tuned with domain-specific data to achieve optimal results in a wide range of applications, such as text classification or offensive message detection. In this study, a comparative evaluation of several pre-trained linguistic models based on BERT (Devlin et al., 2018), a widely recognised type of Transformer, was carried out.

IV-a. Traditional Machine Learning Algorithms

For the development of the traditional models, Python, the scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al., 2011) and Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) (Loper and Bird, 2002) libraries were used. In all cases, the default parameter settings of the scikit-learn library were used. To enhance the robustness of the study, five text representation approaches were used: Count Vectorizer (Suryaningrum, 2023), One Hot Encoding (Hackeling, 2017), TF-IDF (Suryaningrum, 2023), Word2Vec (Mikolov et al., 2013) and Glove (Pennington et al., 2014).

IV-b. Transformer-Based Language Models

Regarding the deep learning models used for our transfer-learning approach, four pre-trained models in Spanish and a multilingual model were selected. All models were implemented in Python, and the HuggingFace Transformers library (Wolf et al., 2020) was used for the training and validation processes.

- **BETO**. The Spanish-BERT model (Cañete et al., 2023) uses a similar architecture to the BERT-Base model and was trained on a corpus that exclusively contains Spanish texts, including data from Wikipedia and the OPUS Project. Specifically, we have used the *bert-base-spanish-wwm-cased* (<https://huggingface.co/dccuchile/bert-base-spanish-wwm-cased>) model.
- **RoBERTa**. A robustly optimized BERT pre-training approach is an improved version of BERT where key hyper-parameters are modified (Liu et al., 2019). There are several versions of RoBERTa pre-trained in Spanish. In this work, models pre-trained with data from the National Library of Spain (BNE) (Fandiño et al., 2022) were used. Specifically, experiments were carried out with the *base* (<https://huggingface.co/PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-base-bne>) and *large* versions (<https://huggingface.co/PlanTL-GOB-ES/roberta-large-bne>). The architecture of *roberta-base-bne* consists of 12 layers, 768 hidden units, 12 attention heads, and 125 million parameters, whereas that of *roberta-large-bne* comprises 24 layers, 1024 hidden units, 16 attention heads, and 355 million parameters.
- **XLM-RoBERTa**. It is a multilingual version of the RoBERTa model (Liu et al., 2019). It was pre-trained on 2.5TB of a filtered CommonCrawl data containing 100 languages (Conneau et al., 2020). In this work, the *xlm-roberta-base* (<https://huggingface.co/xlm-roberta-base>) was the selected version.

IV-c. Balancing Techniques

As mentioned in the Subsection *Dataset Features*, the *hateRADAR-es* dataset exhibits significant class imbalance, a common challenge in machine learning classification tasks. It is necessary to implement approaches that counteract this imbalance to prevent models from prioritizing classification of the majority class. Resampling is the most widely used approach to address class imbalance in text classification, offering a straightforward yet effective solution (Branco et al., 2016). Oversampling and undersampling are two fundamental resampling techniques. While oversampling increases the number of samples from minority classes, undersampling decreases the number of samples from majority classes. To overcome this imbalance problem, in this work we use an oversampling approach to balance the number of tweets from both classes. The aim is that no message is lost in this process as all of them can provide valuable information.

Table 3. Examples of tweets translated to increase the number of positive class cases using single translation.

Original tweet	English version	Translated tweet
Los refugiados musulmanes costarán a Alemania 50.000 millones de euros en los próximos dos años	Muslim refugees will cost Germany 50 billion euros in the next two years	Los refugiados musulmanes costarán a Alemania 50.000 millones de euros en los próximos dos años
Ok, tarjeta sanitaria, casa y 400€ a los refugiados. Ahora que ayuden también a los madrileños que están en situaciones penosas.	Ok, health card, house and 400€ to refugees. Now help also the Madriderers who are in distress.	Ok, tarjeta de salud, casa y 400€ para los refugiados. Ahora también ayudar a los madrileños que están en apuros.
Solución para la entrada y distribución de refugiados en Europa: musulmanes de vuelta a su país o deportados a países musulmanes.	Solution for the entry and distribution of refugees in Europe: Muslims back to their country or deported to Muslim countries.	Solución para la entrada y distribución de refugiados en Europa: musulmanes de vuelta a su país o deportados a países musulmanes.

Specifically, in this work we have applied the oversampling technique known as Data Augmentation by generating new messages of the minority class using *Round-Trip Translation*. This approach is based on translating the original text into another language and then translating it back into the original language. In this way, new examples are generated with a semantic equivalence to the original text, but with variations in the words used. This technique has proven to be effective in increasing the amount of data in the minority class and improving the performance of machine learning models.

Automatic translation between languages often yields messages that are identical, particularly when dealing with short texts, leading to a dataset of suboptimal quality. To address this challenge, we explored two Data Augmentation techniques. One approach involved translating tweets from Spanish to English and then back to Spanish. Using this method, 106 out of the 952 positive class tweets (11.1%) remained unchanged. The alternative strategy encompassed translating tweets from Spanish to English, then to German, and finally back to Spanish. This approach resulted in only 8 messages (0.8%) being duplicated compared to the originals. These

Table 4. Examples of tweets translated to increase the number of positive class cases using double translation.

Original tweet	English version	German version	Translated tweet
Han invadido París. Nadie sabe qué hacer. París quiere rápido desalojo de campamento de refugiados	They have invaded Paris. No one knows what to do. Paris wants quick eviction from refugee camp	Sie sind in Paris eingedrungen. Niemand weiß, was zu tun ist. Paris will schnelle Flucht aus dem Flüchtlingslager	Han entrado en París. Nadie sabe qué hacer. París quiere escapar rápidamente del campo de refugiados
De nada sirve que el CNI analice el perfil de los refugiados que vienen a España si sus hijos en 10 o 15 años pueden radicalizarse también.	It is of no use for the CNI to analyze the profile of refugees who come to Spain if their children in 10 or 15 years can also radicalize.	Es nützt dem CNI nicht, das Profil von Flüchtlingen zu analysieren, die nach Spanien kommen, wenn ihre Kinder in 10 oder 15 Jahren auch radikalieren können.	No sirve de nada que el CNI analice el perfil de los refugiados que llegan a España, si sus hijos también pueden radicalizar dentro de 10 o 15 años.
Alemania sufre de casos de violaciones a mujeres y niño por parte de migrantes refugiados como nunca antes se ha visto #ANREPORTAJES	Germany suffers from cases of rape of women and children by refugee migrants as never before seen #ANREPORTAJES	Deutschland leidet unter Vergewaltigung von Frauen und Kindern durch Flüchtlingsmigranten wie nie zuvor #ANREPORTAJES	Alemania sufre violaciones de mujeres y niños por inmigrantes como nunca antes #ANREPORTAJES

experiments underscore the nuances and challenges inherent in leveraging translation-based augmentation methods to enhance dataset quality.

For the automatic translation process, the models proposed in the OPUS project (Tiedemann and Thottingal, 2020) were used. Specifically, the models used were *opus-mt-es-en* (<https://huggingface.co/Helsinki-NLP/opus-mt-es-en>) and *opus-mt-en-es* (<https://huggingface.co/Helsinki-NLP/opus-mt-en-es>) for translating from Spanish to English and from English to Spanish, respectively. We also used *opus-mt-en-de* (<https://huggingface.co/Helsinki-NLP/opus-mt-en-de>) to translate from English to German, and *opus-mt-de-es* (<https://huggingface.co/Helsinki-NLP/opus-mt-de-es>) to translate from German to Spanish.

In Table 3, several examples of tweets translated using the single translation approach are shown. It can be observed that backtranslation maintains the final text quite similar to the original message. On the other hand, in Table 4, several examples of tweets translated using a double translation approach are presented. With this strategy, it can be observed that the final texts differ more from the original messages.

IV-d. Hyperparameter Optimization

Hyperparameters are adjustable parameters that allow optimizing the performance of a pre-trained model during the training phase. Some of the hyperparameters of Transformers strongly influence the validation results and, therefore, their efficiency. In a language model training process, it is crucial to assign the most suitable values to the hyperparameters. Although certain

values may perform adequately for most pre-trained models, it is essential to conduct a search for the best values for each model, task, and dataset.

IV-e. Ensemble Approaches

Ensembles in supervised classification problems leverage the strategy of combining predictions from multiple individual models to enhance predictive accuracy (Sagi and Rokach, 2018; Mohammed and Kora, 2022). Notable ensemble techniques include hard voting, soft voting, and stacking. Hard voting involves combining the predictions of individual models and selecting the class with the most votes. Soft voting, on the other hand, considers the probabilities assigned to each class by the individual models and averages them to make the final prediction. Additionally, stacking combines predictions from diverse models using a meta-learner, which learns to combine the base models' outputs effectively. These ensemble strategies have demonstrated effectiveness in improving model performance by harnessing the collective intelligence of multiple models. In this work, ensembles have been constructed using hard and soft voting techniques.

V. Experimental Framework

The designed experimental framework, as can be seen in Figure 3, consisted of a series of successive steps aimed at improving the performance of traditional machine learning algorithms and selected transformer-based language models. To evaluate the performance of the algorithms and models, the original dataset was split into a training dataset and a test dataset, with a distribution of 80% and 20%, respectively, using a stratified approach. Table 5 shows the class distribution in the training and test datasets. To provide greater robustness to the experimental framework, performance evaluation was consistently conducted using the same test dataset. In the first phase of experimentation, a baseline was designed to establish a starting point and assess the initial performance of the algorithms and models. For this purpose, the original training dataset was used, which, as described in the Subsection III-c. *Dataset Features*, is an imbalanced dataset.

Table 5. Label distribution in the training and test datasets.

Dataset	Tweets	Label 0	Label 1
Training	4000	3048	952
Test	1000	762	238

The second phase of experimentation involved the application of two data balancing techniques to the original dataset to improve the metrics reached in the baseline. In order not to reduce the number of messages, oversampling techniques were applied to increase the number of hate speech messages. The applied approaches were based on data augmentation, as described in the Subsection IV-c. *Balancing Techniques*. Two new training datasets were constructed, and the algorithms and models were re-evaluated with the test dataset.

Since the results obtained in the second phase outperformed those obtained in the baseline, we proceeded with the optimization process. As will be seen in the VI-a. *Results* Subsection,

Figure 3. Experimental Framework.

the performance achieved by all the transformer-based language models exceeded that achieved by traditional machine learning models. Therefore, for the subsequent experimentation phases, only the optimization of transformer-based language models using the double back translation augmented dataset was considered. This dataset had proven to be highly effective in improving the performance of the language models in previous experiments.

In the third phase, a performance study of the models was carried out by conducting an exhaustive search for the best values of the selected hyperparameters. Finally, in the fourth phase, an ensemble approach was implemented to improve the individual results of the models. To achieve this, the best performing models were selected, and different ensemble methods were applied.

In summary, the experimental framework consisted of progressively applying various optimization approaches to traditional machine learning algorithms and pre-trained language models. The aim was to achieve improved performance in evaluation metrics at successive stages. In each phase, models with the best performance were selected until obtaining the model that achieved the best performance for the task of detecting hate speech towards refugees.

All the traditional machine learning algorithms and transformer-based language models were implemented on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 12GB graphics card.

Table 6. Results obtained by traditional machine learning algorithms on the test dataset using the original dataset. The asterisk (*) indicates the best performing algorithm for each text representation approach.

Text Representation	Algorithm	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
Count Vectorizer	RF	0.86	0.78	0.76	0.54
	XGBoost	0.86	0.79	0.77	0.55
	SVM	0.86	0.78	0.76	0.55
	KNN	0.78	0.65	0.64	0.36
	LR*	0.87	0.80	0.78	0.57
One-Hot	RF	0.86	0.79	0.77	0.56
	XGBoost	0.86	0.79	0.77	0.54
	SVM	0.86	0.78	0.75	0.54
	KNN	0.81	0.66	0.64	0.39
	LR*	0.87	0.81	0.79	0.59
TF-IDF	RF*	0.86	0.78	0.75	0.55
	XGBoost	0.84	0.75	0.72	0.48
	SVM	0.86	0.77	0.74	0.54
	KNN	0.84	0.76	0.74	0.51
	LR	0.83	0.72	0.69	0.46
Word2Vec	RF	0.82	0.65	0.63	0.40
	XGBoost*	0.85	0.77	0.75	0.53
	SVM	0.85	0.77	0.75	0.53
	KNN	0.82	0.76	0.77	0.49
	LR	0.85	0.77	0.74	0.51
Glove	RF	0.81	0.65	0.63	0.39
	XGBoost	0.81	0.71	0.69	0.43
	SVM	0.82	0.70	0.67	0.42
	KNN	0.79	0.68	0.67	0.39
	LR*	0.84	0.77	0.76	0.52

VI. Results and Analysis

In this section, the results obtained from the various experiments conducted are detailed and analyzed. Additionally, our evaluation methods are outlined, and a thorough error analysis is performed.

VI-a. Results

For the evaluation of the generated models, four metrics were used: accuracy, F1-score, area under the ROC curve (AUC-ROC), and area under the PR curve (AUC-PR). Accuracy was calculated using the total sum of correct predictions across all classes; the F1-score was computed as the arithmetic mean of the F1-scores per class, which are the harmonic means of precision

Table 7. Results obtained by transformer-based language models on the test dataset using the original dataset.

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
BETO	0.898	0.858	0.858	0.667
XLM-RoBERTa	0.902	0.855	0.870	0.680
RoBERTa-base	0.897	0.861	0.869	0.669
RoBERTa-large	0.901	0.857	0.844	0.672

Table 8. Results obtained by traditional machine learning algorithms on the test dataset using the augmented dataset with a single back-translation.

Text Representation	Algorithm	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
One-Hot	RF	0.86	0.80	0.79	0.56
	XGBoost	0.85	0.79	0.79	0.53
	SVM	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.59
	KNN	0.77	0.70	0.71	0.40
	LR	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.59

Table 9. Results obtained by transformer-based language models on the test dataset using the augmented dataset with a single back-translation.

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
BETO	0.891	0.853	0.862	0.653
XLM-RoBERTa	0.851	0.815	0.854	0.583
RoBERTa-base	0.876	0.837	0.856	0.621
RoBERTa-large	0.902	0.866	0.869	0.680

Table 10. Results obtained by traditional machine learning algorithms on the test dataset using the augmented dataset with a double back-translation.

Text Representation	Algorithm	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
One-Hot	RF	0.85	0.80	0.79	0.55
	XGBoost	0.85	0.79	0.79	0.54
	SVM	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.59
	KNN	0.62	0.60	0.70	0.35
	LR	0.87	0.82	0.81	0.59

and recall metrics. Finally, AUC-ROC and AUC-PR reveal the classifiers' efficiency across all thresholds and are the most useful measures when addressing tasks with imbalanced datasets. For this reason, the AUC-ROC metric has been used to select the best performing models in the different phases of the experimentation.

Table 11. Results obtained by transformer-based language models on the test dataset using the augmented dataset with a double back-translation.

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
BETO	0.889	0.851	0.860	0.648
XLM-RoBERTa	0.883	0.845	0.861	0.636
RoBERTa-base	0.902	0.864	0.864	0.679
RoBERTa-large	0.889	0.852	0.865	0.650

Table 12. Accuracy (in percentage) of the minority class achieved by transformer-based language models on the test dataset using the original dataset, the augmented dataset with a single back-translation and the augmented dataset with a double back-translation.

Model	Original	Single back-translation	Double back-translation
BETO	78.2%	80.7%	80.7%
XLM-RoBERTa	80.7%	80.7%	82.0%
RoBERTa-base	81.6%	82.0%	79.5%
RoBERTa-large	73.6%	80.7%	82.0%

The first experimentation, as described above, consisted of applying traditional machine learning algorithms and the selected transformer-based language models to the original dataset. For traditional algorithms, parameter values described in Appendix A (Table 18) were used, whereas for transformer-based language models, since optimal hyperparameter values cannot be known beforehand, some commonly used values were employed for fine-tuning the pre-trained language models: batch size of 32, learning rate of $3e-5$, maximum sequence length of 128 tokens, and weight decay of 0.01. Regarding the number of epochs, an early stopping strategy was used to prevent overfitting. For the remaining transformer-based language models parameters, we retained the default values provided by the HuggingFace Transformers library for all the models, using GELU (*Gaussian Error Linear Unit*) as activation function for hidden layers, AdamW as the optimization function and a dropout rate of 0.1. Table 6 and Table 7 show the results obtained for the different selected metrics. For the traditional machine learning algorithms, it can be observed that the combination of the One-Hot text representation with Logistic Regression yielded the best performance for all measures. Furthermore, Logistic Regression was the best performing algorithm for most of the text representations. As for transformer-based language models, they all perform better than traditional algorithms.

Once a baseline was established, the next step was to apply the two data augmentation approaches described above. For a proper comparison of the results, data augmentation was only performed on the training dataset, while the test dataset remained the same throughout all experimentation phases. In both data augmentation approaches, messages with negative content were duplicated, resulting in a new training dataset with 4952 messages and a class distribution of 3048 (61.5%) for class “0” and 1904 (38.5%) for class “1”. The results achieved using the data augmentation approach with a single translation are shown in Table 8 and Table 9, while in Table 10 and Table 11, the results achieved with double back translation are shown. Analyzing

the values of the metrics shown in these tables, it is observed that the values of Accuracy, F1-score, AUC-ROC, and AUC-PR are very similar when using the original (imbalanced) dataset compared to the results when using the augmented datasets. This is because the overall accuracy and error rates (both classes combined) remain relatively stable, as expected. However, when data augmentation techniques have been implemented, a higher rate of accuracy has been achieved for the minority class. Specifically in this task, it is more important to have a higher accuracy rate in detecting the minority class in order to detect as many hate speech messages as possible. [Table 12](#) shows the accuracy rates of class “1” in the test dataset for the four language models. It is noteworthy the increase in accuracy rate when employing data augmentation approaches with respect to the results achieved with the original dataset.

Table 13. Hyperparameter space.

Hyperparameter	Values
Batch Size	[8, 16, 32, 64]
Learning Rate	[2e-5, 3e-5, 5e-5]
Weight Decay	[0.001, 0.01, 0.1]
Optimizer	[“adamw_hf”, “adamw_torch”, “adafactor”]

From this experimental stage onwards, only transformer-based language models were considered since they achieved better performance than traditional machine learning algorithms. In this third phase, a search for the best values of the language models hyperparameters was carried out. [Table 13](#) shows the hyperparameter space used in the experimentation phase. For the remaining transformer-based language models parameters, we retained the default values provided by the HuggingFace Transformers library for all the models, using *GELU* (Gaussian Error Linear Unit) as activation function for hidden layers, and a *dropout* rate of 0.1. Due to the nature of the messages in the dataset, a *max_length* of 128 tokens was used. To perform hyperparameter optimization, the double back-translation dataset was used. A grid search was performed by testing all possible combinations of the hyperparameter space. Optuna hyperparameter optimization software framework ([Akiba et al., 2019](#)) was employed to find the optimal values of the hyperparameters for each model. In the search process, the number of epochs was set to 20 with an early stopping patience of 3 in all cases. A total of 108 runs were performed for each model, resulting in a total of 432 runs. Approximately 20 hours were spent on this search process. The three best combinations of hyperparameter values for each language model are shown in [Table 14](#). The full training dataset was used for the search of these values, and the AUC-ROC measure was selected to optimize the performance of the models.

The results obtained in this phase of experimentation demonstrate that the search for the best hyperparameter values is a very relevant and significant process for improving the performance of transformer-based language models in hate speech detection tasks. [Table 15](#) shows the results reached, for the AUC-ROC metric, by the models fine-tuned with the three best combinations of hyperparameter values. It can be observed that the models trained using the combinations of the best hyperparameter values achieve better performance than those trained with default hyperparameter values. It is important to highlight that, in this optimization

Table 14. The three best combinations of hyperparameter values for each language model. The search was conducted by optimizing the AUC-ROC measure.

Model		Batch Size	Learning Rate	Weight Decay	Optimizer
BETO	hp_1	8	3e-5	0.1	adamw_hf
	hp_2	8	3e-5	0.001	adamw_torch
	hp_3	16	3e-5	0.1	adafactor
XLM-RoBERTa	hp_1	64	2e-5	0.001	adamw_torch
	hp_2	32	2e-5	0.1	adafactor
	hp_3	32	5e-5	0.001	adafactor
RoBERTa-base	hp_1	32	2e-5	0.01	adafactor
	hp_2	64	3e-5	0.001	adafactor
	hp_3	32	5e-5	0.01	adamw_torch
RoBERTa-large	hp_1	64	2e-5	0.001	adafactor
	hp_2	64	2e-5	0.1	adafactor
	hp_3	64	2e-5	0.01	adamw_hf

process, all evaluation metric values achieved by the models with the three best combinations of hyperparameter values on the validation dataset were significantly higher than the values of the models fine-tuned with the double back-translation approach using default hyperparameter values. However, as can be seen in [Table 15](#), the performance on the test dataset, although also higher, is less pronounced. The main reason is that the number of class “1” tweets in the test dataset is smaller, and furthermore, the models have already achieved optimal performance in previous phases. Nevertheless, it can be concluded that the models perform better with a proper choice of hyperparameter values.

Table 15. AUC-ROC values achieved during the hyperparameter optimization process on the test dataset.

Model	Double back-translation	hp_1	hp_2	hp_3
BETO	0.860	0.861	0.867	0.872
XLM-RoBERTa	0.861	0.862	0.870	0.880
RoBERTa-base	0.864	0.866	0.864	0.879
RoBERTa-large	0.865	0.865	0.865	0.879

The final stage of the experimental framework consisted of performing an ensemble approach with the predictions of the models that performed best in the previous phases. The aim was to further improve the prediction by leveraging the predictive capabilities of each model. Since a hard voting approach was used, ensembles with an odd number of models were constructed to avoid ties. [Table 16](#) shows the results of the two ensembles that achieved the best performance in predicting offensive messages towards refugees. The prediction values of the ensembles were higher than the values obtained by the individual models. It can be concluded that the experimental framework has been successful and that very considerable prediction values have

Table 16. Results obtained by ensembles on the test dataset.

Model	Accuracy	F1-score	AUC-ROC	AUC-PR
BETO (hp_3)				
+ XLM-RoBERTa (hp_3)				
+ RoBERTa-large (hp_3)	0.891	0.860	0.892	0.666
BETO (hp_3)				
+ XLM-RoBERTa (hp_3)				
+ RoBERTa-base (hp_3)	0.888	0.856	0.887	0.658

Figure 4. ROC Curve for the three best models and the ensemble model on the test dataset.

been achieved. [Figure 4](#) shows the ROC curve of the three best performing models and the ensemble model.

VI-b. Error Analysis

The previous section outlined the results achieved by the models across various metrics. While they have demonstrated commendable performance, it's imperative to acknowledge that these models are not immune to making occasional prediction errors. To delve deeper into the

factors contributing to these discrepancies, an exhaustive analysis of the model’s mistakes was undertaken. For this study, the model that performed best across all selected metrics was used. Specifically, it was the ensemble composed of the models BETO (hp_3) + XLM-RoBERTa (hp_3) + RoBERTa-large (hp_3). Henceforth, we will refer to this model as *model_ensemble*.

Figure 5. Confusion matrices of the three best performing models and the ensemble model on the test dataset.

From a quantitative perspective, it can be concluded that the models obtained during the learning process have achieved very good performance in detecting tweets with hateful content towards the refugees community, despite the scarcity of such cases in the training dataset. **Figure 5** shows the confusion matrices of the *model_ensemble* and the models comprising the final ensemble, evaluating the results on the test dataset. All three models achieved over 85% accuracy for the minority class. Even the BETO model correctly classifies 90% of the hate

Table 17. Tweets with the manual gold label ('Observed') and the label predicted by the model.

#	Tweet (sp)	Tweet (en)	Observed	Predicted
1	macri no puedes mantener un país y qres recibir refugiados sos un capo!!!!!!	macri you can't maintain a country and you wnt [want] to receive refugees you are a capo!!!!!!	1	0
2	@user 900 euros de pensión x refugiados más 900 de ayuda al alquiler, más ayuda al empleo, y eso lo pagaremos todos	@user 900 euros pension per refugee plus 900 euros rent support, plus employment support, and we will all pay for that	1	0
3	¡calla, demagoga! no es q, algunos, estemos en contra de los refugiados, si lo fueran realmente, es contra los q invad...	shut up, demagogue! it's not t [that], some of us, are against refugees, if they really were, it's against those that invad...	1	0
4	@user enemigo yo? que exageración y en verdad deberías ayudar a los refugiados en ves de decir que te invaden ganarías amistades.	@user me, an enemy? what an exaggeration and you should really help the refugees instead of saying they invade you you would win friends.	0	1
5	entre los refugiados hay violadores -> todos son violadores uno de los agresores sexuales de pamplona era guardia civil -> caso aislado	among refugees there are rapists -> they are all rapists one of the sex offenders in pamplona was a Civil Guard -> isolated case	0	1

speech tweets (215 out of 238) although, on the contrary, it achieves a lower accuracy rate for the majority class (121 errors in 762 cases). It is noteworthy that the ensemble approach has also been successful in reducing and balancing the error rate for both classes classifying correctly classified 89.5% (213 out of 238) of the tweets from the minority class, and 89% (678 out of 762) from the majority class.

For the qualitative study of error analysis, the results achieved by the *model_ensemble* were used. The expert annotators manually inspected the tweets that were misclassified by the model and [Table 17](#) compiles a selection of them. In tweet 1, the classifier was not able to detect hate speech towards refugees as it is a tweet with very subtle hate content. The hatred is mainly directed at *Macri* (Mauricio Macri, president of Argentina from 2015 to 2019) and not at refugees, but at the same time, it supports a classic discriminatory idea in migration studies that a country should prioritize the needs of nationals over foreigners, ignoring the commitment

to international asylum agreements that apply in this case to refugees. The model seems to have missed this subtlety. Tweet 2 is well labelled as it captures the classic stereotype of the immigrant as a profiteer of the system and a burden on nationals. However, the text of the tweet does not contain a hateful message for the model to classify it correctly. Recalling the definition of hate speech used in the annotation, based on (United-Nations, 2021; European-Commission, 2016, 2021, 2023), hate speech or communications include expressions such as spreading suspicion of refugees or association with threats of different kinds, such as those of an economic nature or affecting welfare. Therefore, it is not surprising that tweet number 2 in Table 17 is classified as hate speech in the annotation process because it introduces the author’s dislike and suspicion that refugees threaten economic security and help them be wasteful for the state [@user 900 euros pension x refugees plus 900 euros rent support, plus employment support, and we will all pay for that]. Among the interpretations generated by the tweet, which makes it difficult to classify, is that it indirectly suggests welfare chauvinism (Careja and Harris, 2022), or the preference of nationals over foreigners.

Regarding tweet number 3, it is also well labelled as it subscribes to both the theory that refugees come to invade and the idea that they are not genuine refugees. Since the word “invasion” does not appear in full, the model has not been able to understand this hate speech.

In the case of false positives, tweet number 4 is a difficult tweet to classify because it compares the behavior of refugees with that of other populations. The tweet judges the refugees by generalizing and indicates that they are all rapists. This is hate speech. In contrast, when referring to other sexual aggressors who are different to refugees, it does not generalize and emphasizes that in this case this behavior is an isolated case. Due to the complex comparison between diverse groups, this tweet is very difficult to classify automatically.

Through this detailed study of some of the errors made by the models, it can be concluded that transformer-based language models have a great capacity to address NLP tasks such as text categorization. However, specific techniques are sometimes needed to solve problems inherent to human language, such as irony, ambiguity, or lack of context. As the field of NLP continues to evolve, it is important to develop more advanced techniques that can help language models overcome these challenges and process human language more accurately.

VII. Conclusions and Future Work

This study has significantly contributed to the field of NLP by developing models capable of identifying hate speech directed towards refugees in Spanish social media texts. The *hateRADAR-es* dataset, a corpus of 5000 Spanish tweets meticulously labelled by sociologist and social workers, has proven to be a valuable resource for training and evaluating the machine learning and deep learning models proposed. The results obtained indicate that language models based on pre-trained Transformer, especially those based on BERT and RoBERTa, outperform traditional machine learning methods in hate speech detection, providing superior accuracy and generalization ability. We particularly highlight the performance of an ensemble of transformer-based language models, which achieved an accuracy of 0.891, an F1-score of 0.860, and an AUC-ROC of 0.892. These results not only demonstrate its overall effectiveness but also its ability to correctly identify positive cases of hate speech. These outcomes attest to the potential

of ensembles to handle the subtleties and complexities of language in emotionally charged and biased contexts.

The significance of this work extends beyond its technical contributions. By focusing on anti-refugee hate speech in the Spanish language, we address a significant gap in current research, which predominantly concentrates on English-language texts and non-specific generalizations about groups. This approach allows for a better understanding of the dynamics of hate in specific linguistic and cultural contexts, which is crucial for developing more effective interventions against hate speech in society.

According to the problems generated by the spread of hate speech online, it is clear that in order to achieve successful social integration or inclusion of refugees in ethnically and culturally diverse societies, it is critical to stop the spread of hate speech in social networks towards refugees. As (Soral et al., 2022) point out, the deployment of online hate speech against migrants and refugees is an obstacle to the successful acculturation and well-being of asylum seekers. Likewise, hate speech towards vulnerable people such as migrants or asylum seekers poses a severe challenge and problem for coexistence and democracy in Europe, as well as a risk concerning existing social diversity (Sánchez-Holgado et al., 2022; Arcila-Calderón et al., 2022), which makes the need to advance in the detection of online hate speech towards refugees and other population segments more pressing.

In future works, our interest lies in deepening the understanding of hate speech directed at refugees by incorporating additional nuances and analyses. We intend to expand the dataset to include different subtleties within hate speech, with the goal of developing classifiers capable of detecting various types of hate speech directed at refugees. This will allow us to present both quantitative and qualitative analyses of the results we obtain.

We also plan to explore the integration of advanced generative models and large language models (LLMs), such as GPT-based architectures, to enhance the detection of hate speech, including zero-shot and few-shot learning capabilities. This will allow us to evaluate the performance of these cutting-edge models in comparison to our current approaches and to assess their potential for improving generalizability and robustness in detecting hate speech directed at refugees.

Additionally, we intend to conduct a comparative study between our specialized classifiers and established general-purpose classifiers, such as Detoxify (Hanu and Unitary team, 2020), to better understand the strengths and limitations of each approach in detecting hate speech in Spanish, particularly towards refugees. This comparison will help to position our work within the broader context of hate speech detection research and may reveal opportunities for hybrid approaches that leverage the advantages of both specialized and general classifiers.

Another direction for future research involves exploring the adaptation of our classifiers to other languages, particularly within the Latin American context. This could involve leveraging transfer learning techniques to adapt models trained on Spanish data to closely related languages, thus contributing to the global effort in combating hate speech online. Given the scarcity of resources in languages other than English, we also plan to explore the adaptation of our classifiers to other languages, particularly within the Latin American context, Portuguese and Italian. This could involve leveraging transfer learning techniques to adapt models trained on Spanish data to closely related languages, thus contributing to the global effort in combating hate speech online.

Finally, this work underscores the need for interdisciplinary collaborations involving both technologists and social science experts to ensure that advances in NLP are applied in ways that respect and promote ethical values and human rights. Together, we can use technology not only to better understand hate speech but also to combat it effectively and sustainably.

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Appendix A

Table 18. Parameter values used for traditional algorithms.

Algorithm	Parameter Values
RF	bootstrap: True; ccp_alpha: 0.0; class_weight: None criterion: gini; max_depth: None; max_features: sqrt max_leaf_nodes: None; max_samples: None; min_impurity_decrease: 0.0 min_samples_leaf: 1; min_samples_split: 2; min_weight_fraction_leaf: 0.0 n_estimators: 100; n_jobs: None; oob_score: False random_state: None; warm_start: False
XGBoost	objective: binary:logistic; callbacks: None; early_stopping_rounds: None gamma: None; grow_policy: None; importance_type: None interaction_constraints: None; learning_rate: None; max_bin: None max_delta_step: None; max_depth: None; max_leaves: None min_child_weight: None; n_estimators: None; n_jobs: None reg_alpha: None; reg_lambda: None; sampling_method: None scale_pos_weight: None; tree_method: None
SVM	C: 1.0; break_ties: False; cache_size: 200 class_weight: None; coef0: 0.0; decision_function_shape: ovr degree: 3; gamma: scale; kernel: rbf max_iter: -1; probability: False; random_state: None shrinking: True; tol: 0.001
KNN	algorithm: auto; leaf_size: 30; metric: minkowski metric_params: None; n_jobs: None; n_neighbors: 5 p: 2; weights: uniform
LR	C: 1.0; class_weight: None; dual: False fit_intercept: True; intercept_scaling: 1; l1_ratio: None max_iter: 100; multi_class: auto; n_jobs: None penalty: l2; random_state: None; solver: lbfgs tol: 0.0001; warm_start: False